

Needs assessment:

Growing an inclusive and active community of practice in Digital Humanities and Computational Social Sciences in South Africa

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Summary

Between December 2020 and May 2021 the ESCALATOR team did an extensive web search and several interviews with SADiLaR team members to identify existing challenges to the development of an active community of practice in South Africa. Here we summarise our initial findings.

Further needs assessments and refining will be done throughout the ESCALATOR programme to ensure the initiative addresses the most pressing challenges and benefits the broadest possible range of stakeholders.

Limitation: We acknowledge that the initial searches focused on the terminology “Digital Humanities” (DH) and “Computational Social Sciences” (CSS) which may not be the terminology an applied researcher might use when looking for, or publishing, information about a specific area of these fields. As the community grows we will expand our searches to find relevant online content and update the needs assessments report.

Identified Needs

1. Visibility and findability of training opportunities

Problem

A web search of training opportunities available to researchers and students within Social Sciences and Humanities (HSS) in South Africa yielded very few results.

Solution via ESCALATOR

We created a page on the ESCALATOR website where communities, organisations, programmes, and research groups involved in teaching digital and computational skills to HSS readers can be listed and filtered according to various tags. The community is encouraged to add information via a Google Form that is linked off the page.

Resource: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/initiatives/>

2. Entry level training resources and opportunities

Problem

Many researchers and students within the Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS) still simply don't know where to start when they want to venture into computational or digital methodologies during their research or teaching.

University Library pages for Digital Humanities (findable via search engine searches) link to a limited range of training resources. The [University of Cape Town Libguide for Digital Humanities](#) offered the most comprehensive list of training opportunities and resources available to scholars in South Africa.

Solution via ESCALATOR

We have added a page to the ESCALATOR website where visitors can access learning resources related to various skills relevant to DH and CSS. Most of the resources are available for free and are also published under open licenses which means learners can freely share or reuse them in different training contexts. We encourage the community to add relevant resources via a Google Form.

Resource: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/global-training-resources/>

We are also in the process of developing the Digital Champions Initiative that is a mentorship programme with six different tracks. The Explorer track will offer complete new-comers to digital scholarship an overview of various fundamental concepts via short video introductions.

Resource: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/champions/explorer/>

The Embarker track will be a more hands-on learning opportunity for researchers and students who have had limited experience with digital and computational research practices within HSS but who can commit a few weeks of learning under the guidance of a group of mentors.

Resource: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/champions/embarker/>

SADiLaR has partnered with The Carpentries, a global research data science training provider, to offer introductory workshops in South Africa.

Resource: https://carpentries.org/regions_za/

3. Training opportunities in more advanced DH/CSS topics

Problem

Limited opportunities exist for readers in HSS to learn more advanced computational techniques. One-off workshops are typically not sufficient to learn new material and become competent enough to apply these new skills to one's own research projects or teach it to others.

Solution via ESCALATOR

The Enhancer track within the Digital Champions Initiative will offer researchers and students within HSS the opportunity to hone their skills in specific computational or digital areas by applying them to research projects under the guidance of expert mentors. The track is currently under development but existing mentorship programmes exist where community members can get support in the interim.

Resource: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/champions/enhancer/>

4. Contextualised training resources

Problem

Hardly any training materials available online have been contextualised to be relatable for South African, or even African, learners. Most of the greatest learning materials that are findable online use

examples within the context of the Western world with data sets obtained from the United States, Europe, and further afield.

Solution via ESCALATOR

1. Listing open and free learning resources on the ESCALATOR website.
Learning resources that are useful in the South African context are listed on the ESCALATOR website. Currently the listing does not contain content developed within a South African or African context, but when these resources become available it will be highlighted on the website.

Resource: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/global-training-resources/>

2. Sharing existing contextualised content.
SADiLaR has already started to work on making open course content from South African instructors available via an online learning platform. This is currently still under development but will be shared on the SADiLaR and ESCALATOR websites as soon as it is available.
3. Supporting the development of new content via the Digital Champions Initiative Educator track.

The Digital Champions Initiative will connect researchers and educators wanting to create contextualised content for teaching digital and computational skills within HSS, with programmes and resources offering support in the development of Open Educational Materials.

Resource: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/champions/educator/>

4. Findability of South African research groups, projects, and publications within DH and CSS

Problem

There is currently no exhaustive information available about groups working in the fields of DH and CSS in South Africa. It is almost impossible to track down community members or research projects via institutional websites. It is also not possible to find publications from South Africans using computational methods or digital techniques in HSS research.

Solution via ESCALATOR

ESCALATOR will conduct a desktop study to gather data about existing research groups and projects. This information will be shared via the ESCALATOR website to assist potential funders, policy makers, collaborators, students and others to find information about community members, experts, and stakeholders easily. The data will be available on the website within phase II of the ESCALATOR programme.

ESCALATOR also created a shared open library via Zotero where South African researchers can add their publications demonstrating digital and computational practices within HSS research for others to find.

Resource: <https://www.zotero.org/groups/3866799/dhcssa>

5. Opportunities to become part of the DH and CSS community

Problem

Because there is limited information available online and a limited number of DH/CSS community events are run regularly in South Africa, it's not clear for community members how to connect and grow together.

Solution via ESCALATOR

ESCALATOR has created a Twitter account to share information with our local community and to publicise information about our local DH and CSS community members, projects, resources, and opportunities. We have also created a Slack workspace where DH and CSS stakeholders can connect, ask questions, share ideas, opportunities, and resources.

Resource: <https://twitter.com/DHCSSza>

Resource: <https://escalator.sadilar.org/post/connect-with-the-community/>